

THE GEOLOGY AND GEOPHYSICAL STUDIES OF A GRAVEL DEPOSIT IN UNIVERSITY OF ILORIN, SOUTHWESTERN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Vertical electrical drilling and horizontal profiling methods of electrical resistivity have been employed to study the occurrence of gravel deposit in an area of 3.36sqkm within the University of Ilorin permanent site, Southwestern Nigeria. The petrological characteristics of the deposit were also investigated for assessing its suitability as construction aggregate materials. The gravel deposit varies from conglomeratic sandstone to sand-supported conglomerates. They are unsorted to poorly sorted and dominated by angular to sub-angular pebble clast. Results from the analysis of the geophysical data showed that the study area is underlined by three to four geoelectric layers. These layers are the top soil, the gravel layer, the weathered rock and the fresh basement rock. The top soil is 0.3m-0.9m thick but absent in elevated places due to erosion. The gravel layer is 1.8 – 7.2m with 110-490 Ω m resistivity values. The weathered basement is often undifferentiated from the gravel layer, but where established, it has a thickness of 2.3-8.3m and characterized by 530-5099 Ω m resistivity values. The gravel layer has an average thickness of 3.1m and amounts to an estimated reserve of 20.13x10² tonnes. Depth to the fresh basement rocks is generally shallow, often less than 15m.

High proportion of rough edges (angular/subangular) particles in the gravel aggregates and the abundance of quartz, feldspar and mica minerals which are not chemically reactive with Portland cement recommend the gravel as suitable for construction purposes. Also, the 1:8 ratio of the thickness of the overburden to that of the gravel qualifies the deposit to be an economically exploitable deposit.

KEYWORDS: vertical Electrical Drilling; Horizontal Profiling; Electrical Resistivity; Geoelectric Layer; Overburden, Gravel deposit

INTRODUCTION

Gravel is one of the industrial and building raw materials available to mankind. It is useful in the construction of roads, bridges, houses, dams, just a few to mention. Gravel comprises of different particle sizes which include pebbles, cobbles and boulders. It is a part of clastic sediments resulting from the physical disintegration and chemical decomposition of weathered rocks. Gravel deposit may be residual, elluvial or alluvial. They are often locally derived and accumulate close to or far from source having been transported by running water, ice, wind or shear gravity.

Sedimentologists including Rust (1979), Marek (1991), and Smith and Collins (1993) have defined gravel as an aggregate that contain 50 percent or more of particle greater than 2mm in diameter. In sedimentary formation of Nigeria and particularly in area of thick vegetation cover, rock outcrop are rare and the local geology is not often well elucidated (Ananaba, et al, 1993). Exploitable sand and gravel in these areas occur mostly along the river banks and channels. In the basement complex areas of Nigeria, gravel deposits may be found close to or far from river channels/banks. They are mostly pavement gravel and derived from the physical breakdown and/or chemical decomposition of fractured rocks overlying the fresh basement rocks (Raji, 2004; Olasehinde and Raji, 2007).

Drainage in the area is dominated by the northward flowing Oyun River and its trellis to subdendritic tributaries. These drainages have a NW-SE, NE-SW and in places E-W trends that suggest deep basement fracture-control. Rocks exposures are most prominent along the Oyun River channel and the rocks are highly fractured both at the surface and the depth. The objective of the VES was to obtain information on the resistivity versus depth assuming horizontal layering, with the aim of determining the thickness and other geo-electric parameters of layer(s) which may be interpreted as gravel deposit.

GEOLOGY OF THE AREA

The area under study is part of the Basement Complex of Nigeria considered by various workers to be Precambrian to lower Paleozoic in age (Oyawoye, 1970 and Rahman, 1976). The basement rocks consist of a variety of both migmatized to unmigmatized gneisses, schists, amphibolite and quartzites intruded by 600 ± 150 Ma granitic to dioritic rocks (Oyawoye, 1970; Rahman, 1976).

Fig. 1: Geological map of University of Ilorin showing the study area.

The area has been mapped on a topographic base map on scale 1:50,000. The geological map produced is shown in Fig.1.

Fig. 2 : Sketch map of the Deposit showing VES positions.

Rocks Identified in the area are mainly metamorphic and igneous rocks; they consist;

- (a) The Gneiss Complex: Augen Gneiss; Banded Gneiss; and Granite Gneiss;
- (b) Granite Suite: Foliated Granodiorite; and Foliated Microgranite; and,
- (c) Minor intrusions comprising Pegmatites ; and quartzite veins,
- (d) Quartzites

Banded gneiss, granite gneiss and quartzite generated material for the gravel but are not discussed in detail in this report.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

The field work was carried out between February and June, 2007. The gravel deposit is located at the eastern part of University of Ilorin Permanent campus. The campus is bounded by longitude 4°39'E - 4°41'E and latitude 8°27'N - 8°29'N (fig.1). The main campus of the University is situated at about 15 kilometers east of Ilorin Township and occupies about 15,000 hectares of land.

Plate 1: the Gravel deposit exposed along erosional channel

Plate 2: Sieves and clast sizes

SAS 4000 ABEM Terrameter and its gadgets was used to carry out both Vertical electrical drilling and resistivity profiling. The coordinates and elevations of stations/location were obtained using GPS. Ten (10) Vertical Electrical Soundings were carried out at predetermined locations (Fig 2) with the spacing of locations being 200m to 300m. The resistivity values from each VES position were plotted against half electrode spacing

on a double logarithms paper while the geoelectric parameters(resistivity, conductivity, thickness and depth) of the gravel deposit were optimally estimated using computer software. Resistivity Profiling was carried out to estimate the lateral extent of the deposit. The values of 'a' for the Wenner array was chosen based on the results from the sounding experiments.

Geological mapping was carried out to identify the underlying rock types and their distribution. Also, the petrology of the gravels, in particular their sizes, shapes and roundedness were also studied in order to determine the suitability of the gravel aggregate for construction purposes. Shape analysis was carried out by visual inspection and physical measurement of the particles axes while the particle size distribution was obtained by dry sieving using 1/4- 325 mesh sieve (Plate 2). This allowed assessment of the pebble (4mm-64mm) sized materials which are commonly used for construction.

RESULTS

Qualitative and quantitative interpretations were carried out on each of the VES and Horizontal Profiling Curves using both partial curve matching technique and IP12WIN computer interactive program. Sample of the computer generated curve is presented in Fig. 3 and the summary of the results is presented in Table 1. The results showed a minimum of three and maximum of four geo-electric layers.

Fig. 3: Vertical Electrical Sounding Curve for location 10

The first layer corresponds to the top soil. This layer consists of brownish loose sandy-clay with dispersed sand to pebble sizes litho- and lateritic clasts. The thickness and resistivity of the top soil layer vary from 0.3m to 0.9m and 67.2Ωm to 8214Ωm respectively. The mean thickness is 0.4m, this layer is absent in places (i.e. locations/VES 2 and 5) having being eroded. The second geo-electric layer is the gravel deposit. It has varied 1.8m to 7.2m thickness and resistivity of 110Ωm to 490Ωm. The third layer corresponds to the fractured and partly weathered basement rock. It is characterized by resistivity values of 53Ωm to 5099Ωm and thickness of 2.3m to 8.3m. The fourth geo-electric layer corresponds to the fresh basement rock and it has resistivity values of 2675Ωm to 5196Ωm.

The gravel deposit is very poorly sorted to unsorted with particles ranging from clay to boulder sizes. The very coarse particles are variable mixtures of pebbles, cobbles and boulders and they are dominantly comprised by rock clasts derived

Table 1: Summary of results from interpretation of ten VES data

VES No	No. of layers	Thickness of overburden	Thickness of gravel layer	Depth to the fresh basement rock
1.	4	0.34	1.90	6.70
2.	3	0	3.25	9.10
3.	4	1.00	2.12	6.00
4.	4	0.50	1.90	6.00
5.	3	0	2.50	10.30
6.	4	0.60	6.10	15.00
7.	4	0.30	1.80	6.61
8.	4	0.30	1.90	6.11
9.	4	0.30	2.30	7.90
10	4	0.90	7.20	10.42

from the various underlying lithologies in the immediate vicinity. These lithologies include banded gneiss, granites gneiss, and quartzite. The mineral content is dominated by quartz, feldspar and muscovite with minor tourmaline and garnet.

The particles size histograms (Fig. 4.1) show the gravel is dominated by pebble sized clasts while the shape distribution plot (Fig. 4.2) shows the clasts to be more angular to subrounded. The clasts large sizes and their angular shapes underline their textural and mineralogical immaturity. They are essentially first generation deposition very close to the source (Pettijohn, 1987).

Table 2: Particle size distribution of the gravel aggregates.

Unit of measurements	Silt and Clay	Sand	Granule Gravel	Pebble Gravel	Oversize
Size in mm	<0.0625	0.0625-2	2-4	4-64	>64
Weight (kg)	0.30	5.59	2.71	14.3	2.10
Weight %	1.20	22.36	10.84	57.20	8.40

Fig. 4.1: Barchart showing particle size

Fig. 4.2: Shape distribution of pebble gravel (4-64mm)

RESERVE ESTIMATION

Comprehensive ore reserve estimation is best done through drilling at various points once the deposit has been confirmed by both geological and geophysical studies. Knowing the average thickness and the surface area covered by the deposit, the volume can be calculated as follows;

Surface area of the deposit, $S = 3.36\text{km}^2$
Average thickness of the gravel layer, $T = 3.1\text{m}$
Volume of the reserve, $V = 3.36 \times 10^6\text{m} \times 3.10\text{m}$.
The mean density of gravel is 1.95kg/m^3 (Telford et al, 1976)
The estimated mass of the gravel in the study area=
 $3.36 \times 10^6\text{m}^2 \times 3.1\text{m} \times 1.95\text{kg/m} = 20.31 \times 10^6\text{kg}$
 $= 20,310\text{ tons}$

DISCUSSION

In practice, one of the effective applications of electrical and seismic methods of geophysics is in the investigation of shallow and subsurface deposits, as in the exploration for sand and gravel deposits (Legget and Karrow, 1983; Okwueze *et al.*, 1989). Electrical Resistivity method of geophysics had been employed in the present study to investigate the occurrence of alluvial and residual gravel deposit in part of University of Ilorin main campus. Vertical electrical soundings (VES) carried out showed the gravel deposit as constituting the second geoelectric layer, below the top soil and above the fractured/weathered layer. The thickness of the gravel layer varies from 1.8m to 7.2m, statistically averaging 3.1m.

Horizontal Resistivity Profiling showed that the gravel layer is laterally continuous throughout the mapped area. The thickness of the gravel deposits was also found to increase northwardly towards River Oyun. In addition, there a general decrease in resistivity (increase in conductivity) values of the gravel layer toward the river. Depth to the basement is generally shallow in the area, the highest depth measures 15.00m and the lowest is about 6.00m. Top soil is absent in locations 2 and 5 due to high topographic slope which aided erosion of the topsoil. The gravel is generally coarse. As an aggregate material, the gravel deposit is comprised dominantly by pebble (4mm-64mm) sized angular rocks and minerals particles. Rounded particles occur in minor abundance, less than 10%. The petrological properties (particles sizes and shapes) of the gravel deposit is very comparable and conform with those proved suitable for building and construction purposes. (Smith and Collins,1993) have advanced that suitable aggregate are dominantly comprised by rough edged particles and minerals like mica, feldspar and quartz.

CONCLUSION

The occurrence and abundance of a gravel deposit in University of Ilorin has been investigated using Electrical Resistivity method of geophysics. Aspects of the size and shape petrological characteristics of the deposit were also considered to determine the suitability or otherwise of the gravel for construction purposes.

The gravel deposit occurs as a laterally continuous geoelectric layer with average thickness of 3.1m. It occurs as a very shallow depth, less than 1m. The thickness of the deposit however varies widely up to 7.2m and is dominantly comprised by angular pebble and cobble sized (2mm-64mm) rock particles. The rock particles are formed by weathering and decomposition of lithologies (banded gneiss, granite gneiss and quartzite) in the immediate vicinity of the deposit. Quartz, feldspar and mica are the abundant minerals in the rock clasts.

The study has shown that the deposit is large with a reserve of 20,310 tons. It is a near surface deposit that can be quarried easily by open cast method. The deposit by its very coarse texture, dominantly angular particles recommend the gravel deposit as a suitable aggregate material for building and construction purposes. Geologically the gravel deposit is a residual to alluvial texturally immature sediment.

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